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Key stages in the evolution of the english language

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***Abstract** – This article analyzes the key developments that have shaped the English language over time and its adaptations to various changes in linguistic systems. Additionally, I compare English grammar and resources with those of other widely spoken languages, many of which have evolved over the centuries*

***Keywords:** vocabulary, etymons, compound words, component parts, lexical invasion*

INTRODUCTION

English started as a minor branch but today is the largest in vocabulary and spreading around the world. English was settled automatically by many different citizens from various steps and now the English language is therefore a melting pot with non-phonetic elements that need to be learned thoroughly. The most common of all languages is the Indo-European, of which English is one.

Four thousand years ago, Western Asian languages spread south into Sanskrit and other Indian related languages. It then branched into Europe and over the America. Sir Williams Jones first suggested the concept of so many modern languages having driven from Asia-India (Word origins of English by Marcia Henry ,1987,p:2).He noted there was a similarity in languages to each other. For example, despite having various words all of them, meaning “mother” it has got its’ derivation in the m-m-m of a suckling infant; mama (Italian), mere(French), mutter(German), moder (Danish), mat (Russia).

It was Saga tribe that began spreading English: Angles, Saxons and Jutes conquered Britian during the 15th century. They brought along their languages known as Anglo-Saxon, which we call today Old English. After that, English started becoming rich in its vocabulary and language in the main stages.

- The first stage is when Danish and Norwegian Vikings started invading 787.They speak Old Norse, which a close relative of Old English. After that, they sprinkled their version of words.

- 2nd round is after William the conqueror took over ‘Englaland’ in 1066,For the next centuries, French was the core language of society, the arts and learning.

- 3rd round is the introduction of Latin. When England had hundred years war with France, English became dominant spoken language once more, and English writers started using Latin terms from classical authors. Of the 1.2 million words in English language, many have Anglo-Saxon, Latin, Greek, or French origins.

However, many words that existed in old English did not survive at all into Modern English. Therefore, many modern words in Modern English bear a little resemblance to their Old English etymons. According to some linguists’ analysis as much as 80% of the lexicon of Old English was lost by the end of the Middle English period. For instance, a large compound words like “bookhouse”, ”library”, yet we still preserve the component parts “book”, and ”house”. These lexical invasions did leave some folds in language. Because in French formality, we use “commence”, but in a more ordinary method we just say “start”, using an original English.

During those periods of transitions, other new spellings entered e.g: Normans introduced ou ; g in front of, h as in ‘night’. Linguists are more interested in how words put together, and how the way they put together now is different from how they were put together in the past. We are interested in what the layman often known as “syntax”, which we call grammar. In Japan, word order is completely different from English, such that a sentence like ‘Craig met his wife in Paris’ would come out ‘Crag Paris in his wife’ in Japanese grammar. Or we learn that the use of the -ing progressive form to talk about present tense – She is reading an article- is something that began affecting into the language in the middle English period. In Old English, we would much more likely to put it as “She reads an article”, just as one does in other European languages. But compared to how languages typically change over time, English lost a remarkably vast amount of grammar.

In English language, technological advancements such as the invention of mobile phones and the rise of the internet have not only made different languages available to the public on a global scale, but they have also widened the manner of how language can be used. English has obtained a special status via this advancements and is now considered a world language. This results in different language built as similar as centuries ago e.g in the US “on the weekend” is used, whereas the British have always done things at the weekend, and in school rather than at school.

According to all statistics, despite having undergone irresistible and difficult origin, English is a tongue of immense importance having become the lingua franca of the modern globalized world.

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